

[knowledge base]

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Lattices, Order

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Abstract

LATTICES, ORDER and their underlying definitions and theorems are presented in this white paper (knowledge base).

keywords: lattices, order, knowledge base

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
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Introduction

1. [1,2]

Notation

2. \square := necessarily

3. $x \not\leq y$:= $x \leq y$ is false

4. $\underline{\vee}$:= exclusive or

5. $\exists!$:= exists exactly one

6. $\exists_{\leq 1}$:= there is at most one

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- 7. Def := Definition
- 8. Thm := Theorem
- 9. \cong := order-isomorphism
- 10. \cong_ℓ := *lattice*-isomorphism
- 11. $\mathbb{N}_0 = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$
- 12. $(A \vdash B) := A$ proves B
- 13. $(A \dashv\vdash B) \equiv (A \vdash B \wedge B \vdash A)$

Order (or partial order)

- 14. Def
 - $(P, \leq) :=$ order (or partial order) if $\forall x, y, z \in P$
 - (i) $x \leq x$ (reflexive)
 - (ii) $x \leq y \wedge y \leq z \rightarrow x \leq z$ (transitive)
 - (iii) $x \leq y \wedge y \leq x \rightarrow x = y$ (antisymmetric)
- 15. $P :=$ set; $\leq :=$ binary relation on P

Discrete order

- 16. Def
 - $= :=$ discrete order

Quasi-order (pre-order)

- 17. Def
 - quasi-order (pre-order) := reflexive \wedge transitive $\wedge \neg \square$ antisymmetric

Strict inequality

18. Def

$$x < y \text{ in } P \leftrightarrow x \leq y \wedge x \neq y$$

19. $\leq :=$ order relation

20. \leq gives rise to $<$.

Non-comparability

21. Def

$$y \not\leq x \not\leq y \leftrightarrow x \parallel y$$

Induced order (inherited)

22. Def

$$x, y \in Q : x \leq y \text{ in } Q \leftrightarrow x \leq y \text{ in } P$$

23. $P :=$ ordered set; $Q \subseteq P$

24. Q has the induced order.

25. Q has the order inherited from P .

Chain (linearly/totally ordered set), antichain

26. Def

$$(\forall x, y \in P : x \leq y \vee y \leq x) \equiv (P := \text{chain})$$

(all elements are comparable)

27. Def

$$(x \leq y \text{ in } P \leftrightarrow x = y) \equiv (P := \text{antichain})$$

(there are no comparable elements)

28. $P :=$ ordered set

29. $\text{chain} := \text{linearly ordered set} := \text{totally ordered set}$

30. Notation: $S := \text{chain}$; $\bar{S} := \text{antichain}$.

31. Thm

Any **subset** of a **chain** (**antichain**) is a **chain** (**antichain**).

n -element set

32. $\mathbf{n} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n - 1\}$ is a chain (\leq).

33. $\bar{\mathbf{n}} := \text{antichain of } \mathbf{n}$

Order-isomorphism

34. Def

$$\begin{aligned} \exists \varphi : x \leq y \text{ in } P &\leftrightarrow \varphi(x) \leq \varphi(y) \text{ in } Q \\ &\equiv P \cong Q \end{aligned}$$

35. $P, Q := \text{ordered sets}$

36. $(\varphi : P \rightarrow Q) := \text{map from } P \text{ onto } Q$

37. $(P \cong Q) := P \text{ and } Q \text{ are (order-)isomorphic}$

38. $\varphi := \text{order-isomorphism (it mirrors the order structure)}$

39. Thm

φ is **bijjective**.

40. Thm

$$(\varphi^{-1} : Q \rightarrow P) \equiv \text{order-isomorphism}$$

41. $\varphi^{-1} := \text{inverse of } \varphi$

Number systems

42. Thm

$$\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{N}, \mathbb{N}_0, \mathbb{Q}, \mathbb{Z} \equiv \text{chains } (\leq)$$

43. $\mathbb{N}_0 := \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\} := \omega$

44. Thm

$$\omega \cong \mathbb{N}$$

45. $\cong :=$ order-isomorphism

46. $(n \mapsto n^+ = n + 1) :=$ successor function from \mathbb{N}_0 to \mathbb{N} (order-isomorphism)

47. Thm

$$\langle \mathbb{N}_0, \leq \rangle \equiv \text{order (not a chain)}$$

48. Def

$$m \leq n \leftrightarrow \exists k \in \mathbb{N}_0 : km = n \quad (m \text{ divides } n)$$

Power set

49. Thm

$$\langle \mathcal{P}(X), \leq \rangle \equiv \text{ordered set}$$

50. Def

$$A \leq B \leftrightarrow A \subseteq B$$

51. $X :=$ set

52. $\mathcal{P}(X) :=$ power set of X

53. Thm

$$\forall Y \subseteq \mathcal{P}(X) : Y \text{ is ordered } (\subseteq)$$

Sub

54. Thm: *The set of all (subgroups, normal subgroups, subspaces of a vector space, subrings, ideals of a ring) are ordered under set inclusion.*

Topological space

55. $(X, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space
56. Families of open, closed, and clopen subsets of X can be ordered under set inclusion.

Predicate, power set, order-isomorphism

57. Thm

$$\langle \mathcal{P}(X), \subseteq \rangle, \langle \mathbb{P}, \Rightarrow \rangle \equiv \text{ordered sets}$$

58. Def

$$p, q \in \mathbb{P}(X) : p \Rightarrow q \text{ iff } \{x \in X \mid p(x) = T\} \subseteq \{x \in X \mid q(x) = T\}$$

59. $(p : X \rightarrow \{T, F\}) :=$ predicate (statement true or false)

60. $T :=$ true, $F :=$ false

61. $\mathbb{P}(X) :=$ set of predicates on X

62. $\mathcal{P}(X) :=$ power set of X

63. $\Rightarrow :=$ order relation (implication)

-
64. Thm

$$(\varphi : \mathbb{P}(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(X)) \equiv \text{order-isomorphism}$$

65. $\varphi(p) := \{x \in X \mid p(x) = T\}$

Covering

66. Def

$$\begin{aligned}x < y \wedge x \leq z < y &\rightarrow z = x \\ \equiv x \text{ is covered by } y \text{ (or } y \text{ covers } x) \\ \equiv x \prec y &\equiv y \succ x\end{aligned}$$

67. $P :=$ ordered set; $x, y \in P$

68. $\nexists z \in P : x < z < y$ when $x \prec y$.

69. $\leq, < :=$ order relations

70. $\prec, \succ :=$ covering relations

71. Thm

$$(P \text{ is finite}) \leftrightarrow (x < y \leftrightarrow \exists s : s = (x = x_0 \prec x_1 \prec \dots \prec x_n = y))$$

72. For finite P , $<$ determines (and is determined by) \prec .

Diagrams

73. Check pp. 11-13 of [1].

74. $x < y$ iff there are connected line segments moving upwards from x to y

75. diagram of $\mathcal{P}(\{1, 2, 3\}) :=$ the cube

Order-isomorphism, covering

76. Thm

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi \text{ is an order-isomorphism} \\ \equiv \\ x \prec y \text{ in } P \text{ iff } \varphi(x) \prec \varphi(y) \text{ in } Q\end{aligned}$$

77. $P, Q :=$ finite ordered sets

78. $(\varphi : P \rightarrow Q) :=$ bijective map

Order-isomorphism, identical diagrams

79. Thm

$$P \cong Q \text{ iff } P, Q \text{ have identical diagrams}$$

80. $P, Q := \textit{finite}$ ordered sets

81. $\cong :=$ order-isomorphism

Dual

82. Def

$$x \leq y \text{ in } P^\partial \leftrightarrow y \leq x \text{ in } P$$

83. $P :=$ ordered set

84. $P^\partial :=$ dual of P

85. diagram for $P^\partial =$ diagram for P (upside down)

Duality Principle

86. Thm

$$\forall P : \Phi \leftrightarrow \forall P : \Phi^\partial$$

87. $P :=$ ordered set

88. $\Phi :=$ true statement in P

89. $\Phi^\partial :=$ true dual statement in P

Bottom, Top

90. Def

$$(\exists \perp \in P : \forall x \in P, \perp \leq x) \equiv P \text{ has a bottom element}$$

91. Def

$$(\exists \top \in P : \forall x \in P, x \leq \top) \equiv P \text{ has a top element}$$

92. $P :=$ ordered set

93. $\perp :=$ bottom

94. $\top :=$ top

95. Thm

$(\exists! \perp \in P)$ is dual to $(\exists! \top \in P)$.

96. (95) is an instance of the duality theorem.

97. An infinite chain may not have bottom or top elements.

Lifting

98. **lifting** := adding a bottom element to ordered sets

99. Def

$x \leq y$ iff $x = \mathbf{0}$ or $x \leq y$ in P

100. $\mathbf{0} \notin P, \quad P_{\perp} := P \cup \{\mathbf{0}\}$

101. Thm

$\forall S : \overline{S}_{\perp}$ is an ordered set

102. $S :=$ set

103. $\overline{S}_{\perp} :=$ flat ordered set (lifted antichain)

Maximal, minimal, greatest (maximum), least (minimum)

104. Def

$(a \leq x \wedge x \in P) \rightarrow a$ is a maximal element of Q

105.

$$(a \text{ is maximal} \wedge x \in Q) \rightarrow a = x$$

106. $P :=$ ordered set; $Q \subseteq P$

107. A maximal element is greater than all comparable elements in P , different from itself.

108. Thm

$$(Q \text{ has the order inherited from } P, \exists \top_Q) \rightarrow \text{Max } Q = \{\top_Q\}$$

109. $\top_Q :=$ top element of $Q := \max Q$
:= greatest (or maximum) element of Q

110. $\text{Max } Q :=$ set of maximal elements of Q

111. Thm

$$(Q \text{ has the order inherited from } P, \exists \perp_Q) \rightarrow \text{Min } Q = \{\perp_Q\}$$

112. $\perp_Q :=$ bottom element of $Q := \min Q$
:= least (or minimum) element of Q

113. $\text{Min } Q :=$ set of minimal elements of Q

Disjoint union, linear sum, M_n

114. Def

$P \dot{\cup} Q$ is an ordered set :

$$x \leq y \text{ in } P \dot{\cup} Q \text{ iff } (x, y \in P, x \leq y \text{ in } P) \vee (x, y \in Q, x \leq y \text{ in } Q)$$

115. $P \cap Q = \emptyset$

116. $P \dot{\cup} Q :=$ disjoint union of P and Q

117. Def

$$P \oplus Q := \text{linear sum}$$

(defined by the following order relation on $P \cup Q$)

$$x \leq y \text{ iff } (x, y \in P, x \leq y \text{ in } P) \vee (x, y \in Q, x \leq y \text{ in } Q) \vee (x \in P, y \in Q)$$

118. $P, Q :=$ disjoint ordered sets

119. $P_{\perp} := \mathbf{0} \oplus P$ (lifting)

120. $P \oplus \mathbf{1}$ (P with a new top element)

121. Thm (associativity)

$$P \dot{\cup} (Q \dot{\cup} R) = (P \dot{\cup} Q) \dot{\cup} R$$

$$P \oplus (Q \oplus R) = (P \oplus Q) \oplus R$$

122. Def

$$\mathbf{M}_n = \mathbf{1} \oplus \bar{n} \oplus \mathbf{1}$$

123. $n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$ is a chain (\leq).

124. $\bar{n} :=$ antichain of n

Products

125. Def: $P_1 \times \dots \times P_n$ is an ordered set if the coordinatewise order holds,

$$(x_1, \dots, x_n) \leq (y_1, \dots, y_n) \leftrightarrow \forall i : x_i \leq y_i \text{ in } P_i.$$

126. $P_1, \dots, P_n :=$ ordered sets

Lexicographic order

127. Def

$$(x_1, x_2) \leq (y_1, y_2) \text{ if } x_1 < y_1 \vee (x_1 = y_1, x_2 \leq y_2)$$

Down-set, up-set

128. Def

$$x \in Q, y \in P, y \leq x \rightarrow y \in Q$$

($Q := \text{down-set} := \text{decreasing set} := \text{order ideal}$)

129. Def

$$x \in Q, y \in P, y \geq x \rightarrow y \in Q$$

($Q := \text{up-set} := \text{increasing set} := \text{order filter}$)

130. $P := \text{ordered set}, Q \subseteq P$

Principal

131. Def

$$\downarrow Q := \{y \in P \mid \exists x \in Q : y \leq x\}$$

132. Def

$$\uparrow Q := \{y \in P \mid \exists x \in Q : y \geq x\}$$

133. Def

$$\downarrow x := \{y \in P \mid y \leq x\}$$

134. Def

$$\uparrow x := \{y \in P \mid y \geq x\}$$

135. $P := \text{ordered set}, Q \subseteq P, x \in P$

136. $\downarrow Q, \downarrow x := \text{down-sets}$

137. $\uparrow Q, \uparrow x := \text{up-sets}$

138. $\downarrow Q$ reads *down* Q ; $\uparrow Q$ reads *up* Q .

139. $\downarrow Q$ is the **smallest down-set** containing Q .

140. Thm

$$Q \equiv \text{down-set} \leftrightarrow Q = \downarrow Q$$

141. Thm

$$Q \equiv \text{up-set} \leftrightarrow Q = \uparrow Q$$

142. Thm

$$\downarrow \{x\} = \downarrow x; \quad \uparrow \{x\} = \uparrow x$$

143. $\downarrow x, \uparrow x :=$ principals

Family of down-sets, order-isomorphism

144. Thm

$\langle \mathcal{O}, \subseteq \rangle$ is an ordered set.

145. $P :=$ ordered set

146. $\mathcal{O}(P) :=$ set of all down-sets of P

147. Thm

$$P \text{ is an antichain} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}(P) = \mathcal{P}(P)$$

148. $\mathcal{P}(X) :=$ power set of X

149. Thm

$$Q \text{ is a down-set} \leftrightarrow P \setminus Q \text{ is an up-set}$$

150. $\setminus :=$ set complementation (“subtraction” of sets)

151. Thm

$$\mathcal{O}(P)^\partial \cong \mathcal{O}(P^\partial)$$

(complementation map)

152. $\partial :=$ dual

153. $\cong :=$ order-isomorphism

154. Thm

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{O}(P \oplus \mathbf{1}) &\cong \mathcal{O}(P) \oplus \mathbf{1} \\ \mathcal{O}(\mathbf{1} \oplus P) &\cong \mathbf{1} \oplus \mathcal{O}(P) \\ \mathcal{O}(P_1 \dot{\cup} P_2) &\cong \mathcal{O}(P_1) \times \mathcal{O}(P_2)\end{aligned}$$

155. Thm

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{O}(P_1 \dot{\cup} P_2) &\cong_U \mathcal{O}(P_1) \times \mathcal{O}(P_2) \\ U &\mapsto (U \cap P_1, U \cap P_2)\end{aligned}$$

Ordered relation, down-sets

156. Thm

$$x \leq y \equiv \downarrow x \subseteq \downarrow y \equiv \forall Q \in \mathcal{O}(P) : y \in Q \rightarrow x \in Q$$

157. $P :=$ ordered set, $x, y \in P$

Order-preserving/embedding

158. Def

$$(x \leq_P y \rightarrow \varphi(x) \leq_Q \varphi(y)) \rightarrow \varphi := \text{order-preserving (monotone)}$$

$$(x \leq_P y \leftrightarrow \varphi(x) \leq_Q \varphi(y)) \rightarrow (\varphi : P \hookrightarrow Q) := \text{order-embedding}$$

159. $P, Q :=$ ordered-sets, $\varphi : P \rightarrow Q$

160. order embedding (one-to-one)

161. Thm

$$\varphi(P) \cong P$$

162. $(\varphi : P \hookrightarrow Q) :=$ order-embedding map

163. $\varphi(P) = \{\varphi(x) \mid x \in P\}$

164. $\cong :=$ order-isomorphism

165. $\varphi(P)$ is *embedded* in P .

Composite, order-preserving maps

166. Thm: *The composite of a finite number of order-preserving maps is order-preserving.*

Pointwise order

167. Def: pointwise order

$$f \leq g \equiv \forall x \in \mathbb{R} : f(x) \leq g(x)$$

168. $f, g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

169. $\leq :=$ order relation of maps (functions)

Upper bound, lower bound

170. Def

$$(\forall s \in S : s \leq x) \rightarrow (x \in P) := \text{upper bound of } S$$

171. Def

$$(\forall s \in S : s \geq x) \rightarrow (x \in P) := \text{lower bound of } S$$

172. Def

$$S^u := \{x \in P \mid \forall s \in S : s \leq x\}$$

173. Def

$$S^\ell := \{x \in P \mid \forall s \in S : s \geq x\}$$

174. $P :=$ ordered set; $S \subseteq P$

175. $S^u :=$ set of all upper bounds of S

176. $S^\ell :=$ set of all lower bounds of S

177. S^u reads S *upper* and S^ℓ reads S *lower*.

178. Thm

S^u is an up-set.

179. Thm

S^ℓ is a down-set.

180. Thm

$$\exists_{\leq 1} a, b : a = \text{lub}, b = \text{glb}$$

181. $\text{lub} :=$ least upper bound (supremum) $:= \sup S$

182. $\text{glb} :=$ greatest lower bound (infimum) $:= \inf S$

Join, meet

183. Def

$$(x \vee y) := \sup\{x, y\}$$

184. Def

$$(x \wedge y) := \inf\{x, y\}$$

185. Def

$$\bigvee S := \sup S$$

186. Def

$$\bigwedge S := \inf S$$

187. $(x \vee y) := x \text{ join } y := x \text{ supremum } y$

188. $(x \wedge y) := x \text{ meet } y := x \text{ infimum } y$

189. $\bigvee S := \text{join of } S := \text{supremum of } S$

190. $\bigwedge S := \text{meet of } S := \text{infimum of } S$

191. $P := \text{ordered set}$

192. $\bigvee_P S := \text{join of } S \text{ in } P := \text{supremum of } S \text{ in } P$

193. $\bigwedge_P S := \text{meet of } S \text{ in } P := \text{infimum of } S \text{ in } P$

Lattice, complete lattice

194. Def

$$\forall x, y \in P \exists j, m \in P : j = x \vee y, m = x \wedge y \\ (P := \text{lattice})$$

195. Def

$$\forall S \subseteq P \exists j, m : j = \bigvee S, m = \bigwedge S \\ (P := \text{complete lattice})$$

196. $\emptyset \neq P := \text{ordered set}$

197. $(x \vee y) := x \text{ join } y$

198. $(x \wedge y) := x \text{ meet } y$

199. $\bigvee S := \text{join of } S$

200. $\bigwedge S := \text{meet of } S$

201. Thm

$$\forall a, b, c, d \in P : \\ a \leq b \rightarrow a \vee c \leq b \vee c, a \wedge c \leq b \wedge c, \\ a \leq b, c \leq d \rightarrow a \vee c \leq b \vee d, a \wedge c \leq b \wedge d$$

202. $P :=$ lattice

203. Thm

$$x \leq y \rightarrow x \vee y = y, x \wedge y = x$$

204. $\emptyset \neq P :=$ ordered-set

205. Thm

To prove that P is a lattice is equivalent to prove

$$\forall x, y \in P : \exists j, m : j = x \vee y, m = x \wedge y.$$

206. $\emptyset \neq P :=$ ordered-set

207. Thm

$$\{x, y\}^u = \uparrow y, \quad \{x, y\}^\ell = \downarrow y$$

208. $x, y \in (P := \text{ordered set}), \quad x \leq y$

Power set, complete lattice

209. Thm

$\langle \mathcal{P}(X), \subseteq \rangle$ is a complete lattice

210. Def

$$\begin{aligned} \bigvee A_i &= \bigcup A_i \\ \bigwedge A_i &= \bigcap A_i \end{aligned}$$

211. $\mathcal{P}(X) :=$ power set of X

212. $\bigvee A_i := \bigvee \{A_i \mid i \in I\}$

213. $\bigcup A_i := \bigcup \{A_i \mid i \in I\}$

Lattice of sets

214. Def

\mathfrak{L} is *closed* under finite unions and intersections \rightarrow
 $\rightarrow \mathfrak{L}$ is a lattice of sets

215. Def

\mathfrak{L} is *closed* under arbitrary unions and intersections \rightarrow
 $\rightarrow \mathfrak{L}$ is a complete lattice of sets

216. $\emptyset \neq \mathfrak{L} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(X)$

217. $\mathcal{P}(X) :=$ power set of X

218. Def

\mathfrak{L} is a lattice of sets $\rightarrow \langle \mathfrak{L}, \subseteq \rangle$ is a lattice,
 $A \vee B = A \cup B, A \wedge B = A \cap B$

219. Thm

$\mathcal{O}(P)$ is a complete lattice of sets
(**down-set lattice** of P).

220. $P :=$ ordered set

221. $\mathcal{O}(P) :=$ ordered set of all down-sets of P

M_n , lattice

222. Thm

\mathbf{M}_n is a lattice.

223. $\mathbf{M}_n = \mathbf{1} \oplus \bar{\mathbf{n}} \oplus \mathbf{1}$ (ordered set for $n \geq 1$)

224. Def

$P \oplus Q := \text{linear sum}$

$x \leq y$ iff $(x, y \in P, x \leq y \text{ in } P) \vee (x, y \in Q, x \leq y \text{ in } Q) \vee (x \in P, y \in Q)$

Ordered by division

225. Thm

$\langle \mathbb{N}_0, \leq \rangle$ is a lattice,

$m \vee n = \text{lcm}\{m, n\}, m \wedge n = \text{gcd}\{m, n\}$

226. Def

$m \leq n \leftrightarrow \exists k \in \mathbb{N}_0 : km = n$ (m divides n)

227. lcm := least common multiple

228. gcd := greatest common divisor

Lattice, algebraic structure

229. Def

$a \vee b := \text{sup}\{a, b\}, a \wedge b := \text{inf}\{a, b\}$

230. $a, b \in (L := \text{lattice})$

231. $\vee, \wedge : L^2 \rightarrow L$

232. $\langle L, \vee, \wedge \rangle := \text{algebraic structure}$

233. Thm

\vee, \wedge are order preserving.

Connecting Lemma

234. Thm

$a \leq b \equiv a \vee b = b \equiv a \wedge b = a$

235. $a, b \in (L := \text{lattice})$

Associativity, commutativity, idempotency, absorption

236. Thm: (Associativity) $\forall a, b, c \in L$

$$(a \vee b) \vee c = a \vee (b \vee c)$$

$$(a \wedge b) \wedge c = a \wedge (b \wedge c)$$

237. Thm: (Commutativity) $\forall a, b, c \in L$

$$a \vee b = b \vee a$$

$$a \wedge b = b \wedge a$$

238. Thm: (Idempotency) $\forall a, b, c \in L$

$$a \vee a = a$$

$$a \wedge a = a$$

239. Thm: (Absorption) $\forall a, b, c \in L$

$$a \vee (a \wedge b) = a$$

$$a \wedge (a \vee b) = a$$

240. $L :=$ lattice

Join, meet, order relation, algebraic structure

241. Thm

$$\forall a, b \in L : a \vee b = b \leftrightarrow a \wedge b = a$$

242. Thm

$$(a \vee b = b \rightarrow a \leq b) \rightarrow (\leq \text{ is an order relation})$$

243. Thm

$$(a \vee b = b \rightarrow a \leq b) \rightarrow \langle L, \leq \rangle \text{ is a lattice,}$$
$$\forall a, b \in L : a \vee b = \sup\{a, b\}, a \wedge b = \inf\{a, b\}$$

244. $\langle L, \vee, \wedge \rangle :=$ algebraic structure

245. $\emptyset \neq L :=$ lattice

246. $\vee, \wedge :=$ binary operations

Sublattice

247. Def

if $a, b \in M \rightarrow (a \vee b \in M, a \wedge b \in M)$
then M is a sublattice of L

248. $L :=$ lattice

249. $\emptyset \neq M \subseteq L$

250. $\text{Sub } L :=$ collection of all sublattices of L

251. $\text{Sub}_0 L = \text{Sub } L \cup \{\emptyset\}$

Product of lattices

252. Thm

$L \times K$ is a lattice.

253. Def

$$\begin{aligned}(\ell_1, k_1) \vee (\ell_2, k_2) &= (\ell_1 \vee \ell_2, k_1 \vee k_2), \\ (\ell_1, k_1) \wedge (\ell_2, k_2) &= (\ell_1 \wedge \ell_2, k_1 \wedge k_2)\end{aligned}$$

254. $L, K :=$ lattices

255. Thm

$$(\ell_1, k_1) \vee (\ell_2, k_2) = (\ell_2, k_2) \leftrightarrow (\ell_1, k_1) \leq (\ell_2, k_2)$$

256. $(\ell_1, k_1) \leq (\ell_2, k_2)$ means $\ell_1 \leq \ell_2$ and $k_1 \leq k_2$.

Lattice Homomorphism

257. Thm

f is a lattice homomorphism if $\forall a, b \in L$:
 $f(a \vee b) = f(a) \vee f(b)$, **join-preserving**,
 $f(a \wedge b) = f(a) \wedge f(b)$, **meet-preserving**

258. Def

lattice isomorphism := bijective homomorphism

259. Def

f is a one-to-one homomorphism \rightarrow
 \rightarrow (sublattice $f(L)$ of K) $\cong L$
(f is an **embedding of L into K**)

260. $L, K :=$ lattices

261. $f : L \rightarrow K$

262. $\cong :=$ isomorphism

263. Thm

$$(M \succcurlyeq L) \rightarrow (M \hookrightarrow L)$$

264. $(M \succcurlyeq L) :=$ sublattice of $L \cong M$

265. $(M \hookrightarrow L) :=$ order-embedding

266. Def

$f :=$ **lattice $\{0, 1\}$ -homomorphism**

267. $L, K :=$ bounded lattices

268. $f : L \rightarrow K$

269. $f(0) = 0, f(1) = 1$

Map, order-preserving, homomorphism

270. Thm

$$\begin{aligned} f \text{ is order-preserving} &\equiv \\ &\equiv \forall a, b \in L : f(a \vee b) \geq f(a) \vee f(b) \\ &\equiv \forall a, b \in L : f(a \wedge b) \leq f(a) \wedge f(b) \end{aligned}$$

271. Thm

f is a homomorphism $\rightarrow f$ is order-preserving

272. $L, K :=$ lattices

273. $f : L \rightarrow K$

Lattice/order-isomorphism

274. Thm

$$A \cong_{latt} B \quad \text{iff} \quad A \cong_{\leq} B$$

275. $A, B :=$ lattices

276. $\cong_{latt} :=$ lattice isomorphism

277. $\cong_{\leq} :=$ order-isomorphism

Ideals, filters

278. Thm

$$\begin{aligned} J \text{ is an ideal if} \\ a, b \in J &\rightarrow a \vee b \in J \\ a \in L, b \in J, a \leq b &\rightarrow a \in J \end{aligned}$$

279. Thm

$$\begin{aligned} G \text{ is a filter if} \\ a, b \in G &\rightarrow a \wedge b \in G \\ a \in L, b \in G, a \geq b &\rightarrow a \in G \end{aligned}$$

280. $L :=$ lattice

281. $\emptyset \neq J \subseteq L, \quad \emptyset \neq G \subseteq L$

282. **ideal** := non-empty down-set closed under join

283. **filter** := order dual of lattice ideal

284. $\mathcal{I}(L), \mathcal{F}(L) :=$ set of all ideals and filters of L , respectively (\subseteq)

285. Thm:

$\forall J : J$ is a sublattice of L , i.e., $\forall a, b \in L : a \wedge b \leq a$

286. $J :=$ ideal of L

287. Thm

J is proper iff $1 \notin J$

288. Thm

G is proper iff $0 \notin G$

289. $J :=$ ideal of L with 1 (top)

290. $G :=$ filter of L with 0 (bottom)

291. Thm

$\forall a \in L : \downarrow a$ is an ideal
(principal ideal generated by a)

292. Thm

$\forall a \in L : \uparrow a$ is a filter
(principal filter generated by a)

293. Thm

$\forall J, G : J, G$ are principal

$$J = \downarrow \bigvee J$$

$$G = \uparrow \bigwedge G$$

294. $J :=$ ideal of the *finite* lattice L

295. $G :=$ filter of the *finite* lattice L

296. Thm

$f^{-1}(0)$ is an ideal

$f^{-1}(1)$ is a filter

297. $L, K :=$ bounded lattices

298. $(f : L \rightarrow K) :=$ $\{0, 1\}$ -homomorphism

299. Thm

G is a filter in $\mathcal{P}(X)$.

300. $(X, \mathcal{T}) :=$ topological space

301. $x \in X$

302. $G = \{V \subseteq X \mid \exists U \in \mathcal{T} : x \in U \subseteq V\}$

303. $\mathcal{P}(X) :=$ power set of X

Join, meet, two subsets, ordered sets

304. Thm

(i) $\forall s \in S : s \leq \bigvee S, s \geq \bigwedge S$

(ii) $x \leq \bigwedge S \leftrightarrow \forall s \in S : x \leq s$

(iii) $x \geq \bigvee S \leftrightarrow \forall s \in S : x \geq s$

(iv) $\bigvee S \leq \bigwedge T \leftrightarrow \forall s \in S \forall t \in T : s \leq t$

(v) $S \subseteq T \rightarrow \bigvee S \leq \bigvee T, \bigwedge S \geq \bigwedge T$

305. $P :=$ ordered set

306. $S, T \subseteq P$

307. $\bigvee S :=$ join of S , $\bigwedge T :=$ meet of T

308. $\bigvee S, \bigvee T, \bigwedge S, \bigwedge T$ exist.

309. $x \in P$

310. Thm

$$\bigvee(S \cup T) = (\bigvee S) \vee (\bigvee T)$$

$$\bigwedge(S \cup T) = (\bigwedge S) \wedge (\bigwedge T)$$

Existence, join, meet, finite subset, lattice

311.

$$\forall F \subseteq P \exists s, t : s = \bigvee F, t = \bigwedge F$$

312. $P :=$ lattice

313. $F :=$ finite, non-empty subset of P

314. $\bigvee F :=$ join of F , $\bigwedge F :=$ meet of F

Finite lattice complete

315. Thm: *Every finite lattice is complete.*

Preservation, existing joins and meets

316. Def: φ preserves existing joins if

$$\begin{aligned} \exists j \in P : j = \bigvee S &\rightarrow \exists j' \in Q : j' = \bigvee \varphi(S), \\ \varphi(\bigvee S) &= \bigvee \varphi(S) \end{aligned}$$

317. Def: φ preserves existing meets if

$$\begin{aligned} \exists m \in P : m = \bigwedge S &\rightarrow \exists m' \in Q : m' = \bigwedge \varphi(S), \\ \varphi(\bigwedge S) &= \bigwedge \varphi(S) \end{aligned}$$

318. $P, Q :=$ ordered sets

319. $\varphi : P \rightarrow Q$

320. Thm

$$\begin{aligned} \exists j \in P : j = \bigvee S, \exists j' \in Q : j' = \bigvee \varphi(S) &\rightarrow \varphi(\bigvee S) \geq \bigvee \varphi(S) \\ \exists m \in P : m = \bigwedge S, \exists m' \in Q : m' = \bigwedge \varphi(S) &\rightarrow \varphi(\bigwedge S) \geq \bigwedge \varphi(S) \end{aligned}$$

321. $(\varphi : P \rightarrow Q) :=$ order-preserving map

322. $S \subseteq P$

323. Thm

φ preserves all joins and meets.

324. $(\varphi : P \rightarrow Q) :=$ order-isomorphism

Subset induced order

325. Thm

$$\begin{aligned} \exists j \in Q : j = \bigvee_P S &\rightarrow \bigvee_Q S = \bigvee_P S \\ \exists m \in Q : m = \bigwedge_P S &\rightarrow \bigwedge_Q S = \bigwedge_P S \end{aligned}$$

326. $P :=$ ordered set

327. $S \subseteq Q \subseteq P$

328. Q has the order inherited from P .

Complete lattice, equivalence

329.

$$\begin{aligned} & P \text{ is a complete lattice} \\ & \equiv \forall S \subseteq P \exists m \in P : m = \bigwedge S \\ & \equiv \top \in P, \forall S_{\neq \emptyset} \subseteq P \exists m \in P : m = \bigwedge S \end{aligned}$$

330. $\emptyset \neq P :=$ ordered set

331. $\top :=$ top element

Subset power set, complete lattice inclusion

332. Thm

$$\left(\forall \{A_i\} \subseteq \mathcal{L} : \bigcap_i A_i \in \mathcal{L} \right) \wedge (X \in \mathcal{L}) \rightarrow$$

$\rightarrow \mathcal{L}$ is a complete lattice:

$$\bigwedge_i A_i = \bigcap_i A_i,$$

$$\bigvee_i A_i = \bigcap \{B \in \mathcal{L} \mid \bigcup_i A_i \subseteq B\}$$

333. $X :=$ set, $i \in I$, $\{A_i\} \neq \emptyset$

334. $\mathcal{L} :=$ family of subsets of X

335. $(\mathcal{L}, \subseteq) :=$ ordered set

(Topped) Intersection structure

336. Def

$$\forall \{A_i\} \subseteq \mathcal{L} : \bigcap_i A_i \in \mathcal{L} \rightarrow$$

$\rightarrow \mathcal{L}$ is an intersection structure (\bigcap -structure) on X

337. Def

$$\left(\forall \{A_i\} \subseteq \mathcal{L} : \bigcap_i A_i \in \mathcal{L} \right) \wedge (X \in \mathcal{L}) \rightarrow \\ \rightarrow \mathcal{L} \text{ is a topped intersection structure on } X \\ \text{(closure system)}$$

338. $\emptyset \neq \mathcal{L} :=$ family of subsets of X

Join/meet-irreducibility

339. Def

$$x \in L \text{ is join-irreducible if} \\ (x \neq 0) \text{ and } (\forall a, b \in L : x = a \vee b \rightarrow x = a \text{ or } x = b)$$

340. Def

$$x \in L \text{ is meet-irreducible if} \\ (x \neq 1) \text{ and } (\forall a, b \in L : x = a \wedge b \rightarrow x = a \text{ or } x = b)$$

341. $L :=$ lattice

342. **join-irreducible element** := *cannot* be expressed as the join of any other elements in the lattice

343. **meet-irreducible element** := *cannot* be expressed as the meet of any other elements in the lattice

344. $\mathcal{J}(L) :=$ set of join-irreducible elements of L

345. $\mathcal{M}(L) :=$ set of meet-irreducible elements of L

346. $\mathcal{J}(L)$ and $\mathcal{M}(L)$ inherit L 's order relation.

347. Def

$$\forall a \in P \exists A \subseteq Q : a = \bigvee_P A \rightarrow Q \text{ is join-dense in } P$$

348. Def

$$\forall a \in P \exists A \subseteq Q : a = \bigwedge_P A \rightarrow Q \text{ is meet-dense in } P$$

349. $P :=$ ordered set

350. $Q \subseteq P$

351. Thm

In a finite lattice every element is a join of join-irreducible elements.

Algebraic theory of lattices

352. Thm

$$(L, \leq) \dashv\vdash (L, \vee, \wedge)$$

353. $(L, \leq) :=$ lattice (order relation)

354. $(L, \vee, \wedge) :=$ lattice (algebraic structure)

Equivalence join meet

355. Thm

$$\begin{aligned}(x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z) &\leq x \wedge (y \vee z) \\ x \vee (y \wedge z) &\leq (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z) \\ (x \wedge y) \vee (y \wedge z) \vee (z \wedge x) &\leq (x \vee y) \wedge (y \vee z) \wedge (z \vee x) \\ (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z) &\leq x \wedge (y \vee (x \wedge z))\end{aligned}$$

356. $x, y, z \in (L := \text{lattice})$

Open Invitation

*Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [3,4].
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Supplementary Files

[5]

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